

Electrochemistry of the Acid Polysaccharide from *Lannea grandis*

S. R. Chaudhuri, B. K. Seal and S. K. Mukherjee*

The potentiometric and conductometric behaviour of the degraded and original acid polysaccharides, derived from the exudate of *Lannea grandis*, has been studied under a wide range of experimental conditions. The effect of branching on the dissociation and conductance of these polyacids has been investigated. The equivalent weights of the degraded and original polyacids have been found to be 950 and 1361 respectively. The titration results have been described by a modified form of the Henderson equation: $pH = pK_m + n \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$

The intrinsic dissociation constants of the degraded and original polyacids, determined by extrapolation of the α vs. pK_c curves to $\alpha = 0$, are 4.20 and 4.65 respectively. The concentration dependence of pH at any given α follows a relation of the form: $[pH]_c^\alpha = [pH]_o^\alpha - A C. \frac{1}{2}$ The electrostatic interactions in these polyacids are very weak and decrease with increasing concentration of neutral salts. At comparable concentrations the equivalent conductance of the original polysalt is less than that of the degraded sample. A semiquantitative estimate of counterion-association has been reported.

The behaviour of polymeric electrolytes in solution is largely determined by the electrostatic free energy arising from the dissociation of the ionogenic groups from the polymer back-bone, which, again, is accompanied by a change in size and shape of the macroions in solution. The variation of structural changes as a function of charge on the degraded and original acid polysaccharides, derived from the exudate of *Lannea grandis*, has been demonstrated while dealing with viscosity measurements and the results have been reported elsewhere¹. The object of the present investigation has been to examine the effects of branching on the dissociation and conductance of the polybasic acids and to throw further light on the constitution of these gum polysaccharides. According to Bhattacharya and Rao² the original polyacid consists of a long chain of galactose and galacturonic acid together with short chains of arabinose, the latter being situated along side-chains, whereas the degraded polyacid, produced by autohydrolysis of the original polyacid, consists of a linear chain of galactose and galacturonic acid only.

EXPERIMENTAL

The isolation and purification of the acid polysaccharides have been described earlier¹.

Potentiometric measurements were carried out with a Cambridge pH -meter (Bench model) equipped with Cambridge glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode with an agar salt-bridge, and with proper temperature control settings. The solutions were made in conductivity water and measurements were done in the range of 28-30°. The

*Present address: University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, W. B.

1. S. R. Chaudhuri, and S. K. Mukherjee, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 679.

2. A. K. Bhattacharya, and C. V. N. Rao, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 107.

instrument was calibrated as often as necessary with standard buffer solutions of pH 's 4.0, 6.98 and 9.18, in order to correct for any asymmetry that might have developed on the glass surface. The measurements were accurate within ± 0.02 units.

Conductance measurements were made in a Kohlrousch type of cell (cell constant = 0.252 cm^{-1}), using a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge operated at $30.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The solutions were made in conductivity water with usual precautions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Potentiometric Titration. The equivalent weights of the degraded and original polyacids are 950 and 1361 respectively as calculated from the titration curves.

Since the activity of the $-\text{COO}^-$ ions in this case cannot be determined precisely, a "cocentration dissociation constant" K_c has been defined as

$$K_c = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} \times C_{-\text{COO}^-}}{C_{-\text{COOH}}}$$

the concentrations being expressed in equivalents per litre. For electroneutrality the concentrations of the different ionic species in the system should follow the relation,

$$C_{\text{H}^+} + C_{\text{Na}^+} = C_{-\text{COO}^-} + C_{\text{OH}^-}$$

Here C_{Na^+} represents the concentration of the sodium ions in the solution and is equivalent to the amount of NaOH added. C_{OH^-} in an acid solution may be neglected. The

only unknown quantity $C_{-\text{COO}^-}$ can now be determined. The values of pK_c have been plotted against $\frac{C_{-\text{COO}^-}}{C_{-\text{COO}^-} + C_{-\text{COOH}}}$ both for the degraded and original polyacids and the results are shown in Fig. 1. It is evident from the figure that the values of pK_c increase with increasing degree of dissociation, a fact in conformity with polyelectrolyte behaviour. However, the slopes of the α vs. pK_c curves are very small which suggests that the uronic-carboxyl groups are so widely apart on the polymer chain that electrostatic interaction among them is considerably weak. Extrapolation of the α vs. pK_c curves to $\alpha = 0$ for the two polyacids gave the values of the corresponding intrinsic dissociation constants, (pK_0), which are recorded in Table 1. Tanford³, while analysing the results on

FIG. 1. Plots of pK_c vs. α of the polyacids
Degraded polyacid O; Original
polyacid ●

FIG. 2. Plots of $pH - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ vs. α of the
polyacids. Degraded polyacid O; Original
polyacid. ●

polymethacrylic acid obtained by Arnold and Overbeek⁴, suggested that for polyelectrolytes, a plot of $pH - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ vs α on extrapolation should yield the value of pK_0 . These graphs are shown in Fig. 2* and the values of pK_0 obtained from them are given in Table 1.

TABLE I
Intrinsic dissociation constants (pK_0) of the polyacids

Polyacid	pK_0 from pK_c vs. α plot	pK_0 from $pH - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ vs α plot
Degraded	4.20	4.30
Original	4.65	4.75

It is interesting to note that the intrinsic dissociation constants for each of the polyacids derived by means of two distinctly different methods are in good agreement. The pK_0 -value of the original polyacid is, however, a bit higher than that of the degraded polyacid. This slight increase in pK_0 of the original polyacid may be ascribed to branching of arabinose molecules, which perhaps helps formation of hydrogen bonds and thereby hinders dissociation of the carboxylic H^+ ion. Incidentally, it may be mentioned that the lack of dependence of pH on the molecular weights of the polyacids has been verified by a number of workers^{4,5,6}.

The acid behaviour of the carboxyl groups in polyelectrolytes has often been described by a modified form of the Henderson equation

$$pH = pK_m + n \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$$

where pK_m is the value of pH at half-neutralisation and n is an empirical index of intramolecular electrostatic interactions⁶. The values of pK_m and n have been found to depend on the nature of the polymer, concentration of the polyion, distance between the carboxyl groups along the polymer backbone and also on the concentration of neutral salts in the system.

Since pK_m and n are dependent on polyacid concentration, it is necessary to extrapolate the results to infinite dilution in order to obtain the unequivocal titration equation. To achieve this objective, pH -values of the solutions for different concentrations at a given value of α of the polyacids were measured. The results for the degraded and original polyacids are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. The concentration dependence of pH for different values of α has been found to follow an equation of the form :

$$[pH]_c^\alpha = [pH]_0^\alpha - A c^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

*Since at the lowest α values even a trace of CO_2 might affect the pH measurement, the pH value at this α was not considered good enough for extrapolation.

4. R., Arnold, and J. T. G., Overbeek, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1950, **69**, 192.

5. A. Katchalsky, and P. Spitnik, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1947, **2**, 432.

6. W. Kern, *Biochem. Z.*, 1939, **301**, 338.

FIG. 3. Plots of pH vs. $c^{1/2}$ of the degraded polyacid at different degrees of neutralisation.

FIG. 4. Plots of pH vs. $c^{1/2}$ of the original polyacid at different degrees of neutralisation.

where c is the concentration of the polyacids in equivalents per litre, $[pH]_c^\alpha$ is the pH at a concentration c and degree of dissociation α , $[pH]_0^\alpha$ is the pH extrapolated to infinite dilution and at a degree of dissociation α . Values of $[pH]_0^\alpha$ obtained by extrapolation have been plotted against $\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ in Fig. 5. It is seen that the "infinite dilution titra-

FIG. 5. Infinite dilution titration curves of the polyacids.
Degraded polyacid O; Original polyacid

tion equation" for the degraded polyacid is given by

$$pH = 5.66 + 0.93 \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$$

and the corresponding equation for the original polyacid is given by

$$pH = 5.45 + 0.87 \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$$

Thus it is seen that at infinite dilution the values of pK and the corresponding values of n for the original as well as the degraded polyacids are in good agreement with each other. This suggests identical stereochemical positions of the carboxyl groups in them. It may be noted that the value of n in the modified Henderson equation for polybasic acids is generally greater than 1, and it becomes 1 for monobasic acids. In the present case, however, the values of n for the degraded and original polyacids are close to unity. This

suggests that the interaction, if any, between dissociating groups of the polyacid is not strong enough to affect the potentiometric measurements.

In Fig. 6 pH values of the degraded polyacid in presence of varying concentrations of sodium chloride have been plotted against $\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ in accordance with the modified Henderson equation. The values of pK_m and n which may be taken as a measure of electrostatic interactions, are shown in Table II.

FIG. 6. Plots of pH vs. $\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ of (a) degraded polyacid in (1) water \circ ; (2) 0.1 N NaCl \circ (3) 0.5 N NaCl \bullet ; and (b) original polyacid in water. \bullet

TABLE II

Variation of pK_m and n of the degraded polyacid as a function of ionic strength.

Concn. of NaCl	pK_m	n
0.00 (water)	4.40	1.25
0.1 N	4.05	1.08
0.5 N	3.80	1.04

The values of pK_m and n for the original polyacid in water are 4.80 and 1.39 respectively, which differ slightly from those of degraded polyacid as shown above. It may be noted from the above results that the values of pK_m and n decrease with increasing concentration of sodium chloride. At a salt concentration of 0.5 N the value of n is 1.04, indicating a close approach to the behaviour of a monobasic acid ($n=1$). The value of pK_m (3.8) at this salt concentration is also in close agreement with the pK value of galacturonic acid (3.42). It is evident, therefore, that the presence of a large excess of neutral salt (e.g., 0.5 N NaCl) suppresses, almost completely, the electrostatic interactions in these polyacids, so that their behaviour is identical with monobasic acids.

Conductance Behaviour: The variation of equivalent conductance as a function of concentration of the sodium salts of both the degraded and original polyacids has been shown in Fig. 7. It is evident from this Figure that at the higher range of concentrations studied, the rate of increase of equivalent conductance with dilution is very small, but as the concentration is gradually decreased the equivalent conductance begins to rise at a relatively rapid rate. The stiff rise in equivalent conductance with dilution is in fact a very characteristic feature differentiating polyelectrolytes from simple salt solutions, the cause of this rapid rise is, however, only poorly understood. The polymer chain represents

a region of high charge density and consequently, it attracts the oppositely charged sodium ions into the polymer coil some of which are actually paired off with the -COO^- ions, while others form the counter-ion atmosphere around the polymer chain. These polyionic clusters form the whole kinetic units, the net charge on them being the difference between the number of the -COO^- groups and that of the bound sodium ions. With increasing dilution, more of the counterions will diffuse away from the polymer coil. Consequently, the number of free sodium ions as well as that of the ionogenic sites on the polyion will increase. The net result would be a progressive increase of equivalent conductance as we pass on to more dilute solutions. It is interesting to note that at comparable concentrations the equivalent conductance of the original polysalt is always less than that of the degraded sample. Such a result is quite expected, because the original polysalt, due to the presence of branching, is more bulky than the degraded polysalt so that the mobility of the former should be less than that of the latter.

FIG. 7. Variation of equivalent conductance with concentration of the polysalts: Degraded polysalt O; Original polysalt ●

In formulating a satisfactory concept of polyelectrolyte solutions, it is necessary to know to what extent the counterions are associated with the polyions. The problem of counterion association with polyacids has been solved by Wall *et al.*⁷ in an elegant manner by the use of radioactive tracer elements. In order to make a semi-quantitative estimate of the extent of counterion association with the extent of neutralisation, the method of Oth and Doty⁸ was employed in the present investigation. Specific conductances, K , were measured with dilution at different degrees of neutralisation of the degraded polyacid. The plot of K/c vs. $c^{1/2}$ on extrapolation gave the value of the limiting reduced specific conductance, $[K/c]_0$ whence the limiting molar conductance, $\Lambda_0 = 1000 \times [K/c]_0 \times \text{mol. wt/equiv. wt. mputed.}$ Molecular weight of the degraded polyacid, as determined by

7. J. R. Huizenga, P. F. Grieger and F. T. Wall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2636, 4228.

8. A. Oth, and P. Doty, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 43.

light scattering⁹ measurements, has been found to be 8.21×10^5 . The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Limiting reduced specific conductance and molar conductance as a function of degree of neutralisation.

α	$[K/c]_0$	$\Lambda_0 \times 10^{-5}$	$[\eta]$ (dl/gm)
0.20	0.12	1.02	0.33
0.40	0.12	1.09	0.40
0.60	0.14	1.20	0.43
0.80	0.15	1.31	0.71
1.00	0.19	1.63	0.48

If λ^-_0 be the limiting molar conductance of the polyion, Z' the effective charge on the polyion and λ^+_0 the equivalent conductance of the counterion ($\lambda_{Na^+} = 55.3$ Ohms⁻¹ cm.² at 30°), we get,

$$\Lambda_0 = Z' \lambda^+_0 + \lambda^-_0$$

Now the mobility, μ , of the polyion is given by the expression

$$\mu = (\Lambda_0 - Z' \lambda^+_0) / Z' \cdot F$$

The mobility can also be expressed as

$$\mu = (H \cdot e \cdot Z') / f$$

where H represents the applied electric field, e the electronic charge and f = the frictional coefficient of the migrating particle. If it is assumed that the frictional coefficient is proportional to the intrinsic viscosity, i.e., $f = k[\eta]$, then by combining the two preceding equations and taking all the constants into a single one, D , equal to $D = H \cdot e \cdot F / k$, we get

$$\frac{D Z'^2}{[\eta]} + \lambda^+_0 Z' - \Lambda_0 = 0$$

Thus if D is known, it is possible to evaluate Z' from known values of $[\eta]$, λ^+_0 and Λ_0 .

Since D is not independently known, we can make an estimate of it by assuming that for low values of α , e.g., for α up to about 20%, the effective number of charges, Z' , is equal to the titration charges, αZ , (where Z , is the total theoretical charge, given by

TABLE IV

Calculated and titration charges of the polyion as a function of degree of neutralisation.

α	Calculated charge Z'	Titration charge Z	Percentage of bound Na^+
0.20	173	173	—
0.40	195	346	43
0.60	214	519	59
0.80	284	691	59
1.00	235	864	73

9. S. R. Chaudhuri and S. K. Mukherjee, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 679.

mol. wt./equiv. wt.). Then with this value of D , the effective charge at various α 's may be calculated. The difference between the effective charge and the titration charge of the polyion is a measure of the bound Na^+ ions. The results are shown in Table IV.

It is evident that the net charge per polyion at higher degree of neutralisation is considerably lower than the titration charge which can only happen due to fixation of counterions on the polymer chain as a result of high charge density at larger values of the degree of neutralisation. It should be remarked, however, that these results are of semi-quantitative significance only.

DEPARTMENT OF MACROMOLECULES,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE
CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA—32.

Received November 23, 1966.